

THE QUESTION OF DIRECTING STUDENTS TO PROFESSIONAL EDUCATION

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Introduction. In various interpretations, both scientific and reference literature, the field of education is understood as a complex of structural features that reflect the peculiarities, laws of the cultural space of an educational institution and a particular society. In addition to this concept, state documents on education, modern pedagogical research and scientific work use the concept of “field of Education”, which means “the unity of educational, extracurricular and socially significant activities of students. Creating such an environment requires the teacher to constantly creatively search for new effective forms and technologies, organizational foundations and innovative tools” [4].

The analysis of these concepts gives reason to believe that their content reveals common aspects, among which it is possible to note educational and social activities of social importance. Modern comprehensive schools are successfully implementing certain areas of this activity in practice. Through the efforts of students and teachers in a number of schools, educational work is organized, participation in concerts, introduction of scientific innovations, Organization of student conferences, festivals, forums and Olympiads, participation in volunteering projects, creation of special websites, and participation in various socially significant youth movements.

Analysis of thematic literature. Questions of healthy lifestyle and its philosophical aspects in students, philosophical foundations of interaction of educational institutions and civil society institutions in the formation of personality, problems of healthy lifestyle of young people with disabilities and their pedagogical, psychological characteristics, socio-political activity of young people in the formation of civil society, increasing legal literacy, improving the system of social protection K.Najmiddinova [3], M.Kholmatova [5], P.Khudoybergenova [6], X.As studied by shaykhova [7] et al., they studied the spirituality, culture of the individual, the role of spiritual culture in increasing his social activity, a healthy lifestyle and its philosophical aspects.

Ensuring the tasks and interaction of the subjects of the innovative cluster of pedagogical education is a complex, multidisciplinary scientific and practical process. Combining several types of interrelationships around a common goal

requires anic calculations and scientific solutions, projects with guaranteed results.

Today, all forms, methods and technologies of Educational, Scientific, methodological, educational tools and management-related cooperation on each branch are introduced into practice, based on the specifics of the sphere by integrating the functions of the family, preschool educational organization, School, higher educational institution, neighborhood and municipalities as subjects of the pedagogical educational cluster.

Research methodology. By the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 21, 2023 “on measures aimed at radically increasing the role of the neighborhood Institute in society and ensuring its functioning as a first link in solving population problems”, the “neighborhood seven” is established, the tasks of each employee are set, the chairman of the neighborhood is noted to

The upbringing of a harmonious, perfect person in every possible way is one of the pressing issues facing our society, and the significant social, economic and political changes that are taking place will not remain without affecting the minds of young people. The work of educating the younger generation as spiritually-morally, culturally-educationally mature people begins primarily with the family. In this regard, the cooperation of parents, neighborhoods and educational institutions plays an important role in raising a harmonious generation.

In particular, establishing this cooperation properly is an important nurturing tool in preventing adolescents from engaging in neglect, disorderly conduct, crime, and similar household disorders.

When dealing with the upbringing of the younger generation, parents in the family, neighbors and the general public in the neighborhood, teachers and coaches in an educational institution are responsible for the perfection of the next generation.

Preschool education is the initial type of the system of continuing education and creates the necessary organizational, methodological, psychological, pedagogical conditions for the upbringing of healthy, comprehensively mature children. Helps parents in preparing children for regular schooling. The preschool organization is an educational and health-improving institution and plays a huge role in strengthening educational cooperation with the family, forming the personality of the child, developing his interests in knowledge, ensuring the intellectual, personal and physical development of the child,

introducing children to the rich national, cultural and historical heritage of the people.

Within the framework of activities carried out as a result of the interaction of the school and preschool educational institution, it will be possible to form national feelings of pride, patriotism in children, to form the need for children to acquire knowledge, sources of desire to study, to prepare them for the educational process in regular reading.

It is also the tasks of the subjects of the innovative cluster of pedagogical education that general secondary educational institutions should visit professional colleges and academic lyceums as part of the work of vocational orientation of students, to introduce the rules of admission to higher educational institutions, directions of education and specialties.

Vocational guidance was carried out by higher education institutions along with presentations, videos, presentations and promotional booklets. [2] Such career orientation activities are carried out through interesting lectures, heated conversations and discussions of professors and teachers of departments of higher educational institutions.

Conclusions and suggestions. The pedagogical basis of the innovative cluster of pedagogical education is a flexible educational environment, prevention of “professional fading”, pedagogical profitability, SMART sensory, mixed education, educational receptors, pedagogical improvisation, pedagogical Concilium (briefing), Educational Service, individual education, etc.

Its psychological foundations are academic and professional mobility, repetition interval, relative and disproportionate perception (memory), pedagogical-psychological diet (orientation corresponding to the need for education, presentation of knowledge and acceptance of the most important ones), human capital.

Ensuring the tasks and interaction of the subjects of the innovative cluster of pedagogical education is a work of state significance in a broad sense, leading to the formation of a morally healthy, spiritually rich, strong family in all organizations, labor communities, society as a whole, strengthening the care of young people with the future of the country.

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